

D.M.E. Behaviour of Copper(II)-Glycylglycine and Copper(II)-Glycylglycine-Imidazole Systems

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Polarographic behaviour of the binary system copper(II)-glygly and ternary systems copper(II)-glygly-ImH (1 : 1 : 0.5 and 1 : 1 : 1) have been studied at d.m.e. The polarographic waves for various species formed have been identified. The imidazole bridged binuclear copper(II) complex of glygly undergoes one-step reversible reduction suggesting simultaneous two-electron reduction of the two copper centres. It has been proposed that the bridging imidazolate ion accepts the electrons from the d.m.e. and transfers them simultaneously to the two copper centres.

THE active site of the bovine erythrocyte superoxide dismutase has Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions bridged by imidazolate of the histidine residue¹. The structure of the active site changes with pH. At low pH the imidazolate bridge is broken. At high pH the Cu^{II} ion migrates intermolecularly to another zinc binding site to form an imidazolate bridged Cu^{II}-Cu^{II} system. Imidazolate bridged binuclear copper(II) complexes are, therefore, important as models for the active site of the bovine erythrocyte superoxide dismutase. A symmetrical copper(II) binuclear complex in which two Cu^{II}-glygly complexes are linked by an imidazolate bridge (I) has recently been chosen as a simple model for this² purpose.

Matsumoto *et al.*³ prepared this binuclear complex in solid state and reported its crystal structure. Sato *et al.*⁴ studied the formation of complex in solution and reported the equilibrium constants for the formation and scission of the imidazolate bridge linkage. In the present communication, we report the reduction of this bridged species (I) at the dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.). For the purpose polarograms have been reported for Cu^{II}-glygly (1 : 1) and Cu-glygly-imidazole (1 : 1 : 0.5 and 1 : 1 : 1). The d.m.e. behaviour of several related binary and ternary complex species are also reported.

Experimental

Polarograms were recorded with a Systronics 1632 polarograph in conjunction with a Systronics 1501 recorder with a three-electrode set-up. The capillary used has the following characteristics at open-circuit: $h=85$ cm, $m=1.50$ mg s⁻¹, $t=3.2$ s. The temperature was maintained at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The pH was measured by a Naina NIG-333 digital pH-meter with an accuracy of 3.05 pH unit.

The stock solution of the metal was prepared by dissolving copper(II) chloride in conductivity water and standardised iodometrically. Solutions of glycylglycine (Sigma) and imidazole (Kotchligh) were prepared in conductivity water. Sodium perchlorate (AnalaR) was used as a supporting electrolyte and Triton-X-100 (Rhom and Hoas) as a maximum suppressor.

Method: Polarograms of the three complex systems in which Cu^{II}-glygly-ImH ratios were 1 : 1 : 0, 1 : 1 : 0.5 and 1 : 1 : 1 were recorded in the pH range 4.0–11.5. The test solution was deaerated by purging pure nitrogen. In each system, pH was maintained using dilute solutions of NaOH and HCl.

Results and Discussion

The polarographic half-wave potentials are presented in Table 1. Well-defined diffusion-controlled waves were obtained in all the cases. Reduction of copper(II) yielded diffusion current of the magnitude lying in the range from which two-electron reduction may be inferred. The plots of $E_{a.s.}$ vs $\log(i_a - i)/i$ were linear. The criterion of diffusion-controlled nature of the depolariser is the constancy of $i_a/h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ value at different heights of the mercury column. Studies have been carried out on the binary system Cu^{II}-glygly and on the ternary system⁵ Cu^{II}-glygly-imidazole.

Binary system $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-glygly}$: $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-glygly}$ system has been exhaustively studied by earlier workers⁴⁻¹¹ who proved that the main species obtained for

The polarograms obtained for the system $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-glygly}$ (1 : 1) at different pH values are shown in Fig. 1. The results show only one polarographic wave at pH 4.0; at pH 5.0, a second wave appears. As the pH is raised the second wave gains height at the cost of the first wave, which persists, though with very small i_d , even in alkaline medium. Variation in i_d and $E_{1/2}$ of the two waves with change in pH is shown in Fig. 2. The first wave may be attributed to species 1. With increase in pH, the first wave becomes shorter which is apparently due to rightwards shift in the equilibrium $1 \rightleftharpoons 2$. Also the change in the $E_{1/2}$ value of the first wave with increase in pH indicates deprotonation of the species 1.

The second wave appearing at pH 5.0 is evidently due to the species 2. Increase in height of the second wave with the increase in pH is again due to the equilibrium $1 \rightleftharpoons 2$. At $\text{pH} \approx 8.0$, the second wave attains maximum height, indicating that the rightwards shift of the equilibrium $1 \rightleftharpoons 2$ is almost complete at $\text{pH} \approx 8.0$. With increase in pH, $E_{1/2}$ of the second wave records a small shift towards less negative value upto pH 8.0. This observation suggests that the equilibrium $1 \rightleftharpoons 2$ is the rate-determining step in the reduction of species 2. After the rightwards shift of equilibrium $1 \rightleftharpoons 2$ is complete at $\text{pH} \approx 8.0$, the reduction of the species 2 follows normal trend regarding the pH-dependence of the $E_{1/2}$ value. The $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards more negative

TABLE 1—HALF-WAVE POTENTIALS (NEGATIVE, IN V VS S.C.E.) OF VARIOUS POLAROGRAPHIC WAVES OBSERVED AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES FOR DIFFERENT COMPOSITIONS OF THE SPECIES

System	pH	1	2	3	4
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-glygly-ImH}$ 1 : 1 : 0	4.00	0.054	0.00	—	—
	5.00	0.054	0.362	—	—
	6.00	0.090	0.861	—	—
	7.00	0.116	0.952	—	—
	8.00	0.155	0.941	—	—
	9.00	0.167	0.865	—	—
	10.00	0.167	0.999	—	—
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-glygly-ImH}$ 1 : 1 : 0.5	10.15	0.205	0.484	—	—
	11.50	0.224	0.968	—	—
	4.00	0.051	—	—	—
	5.00	0.055	0.392	—	—
	6.00	0.188	0.897	0.862	—
	7.00	—	0.402	0.414	—
	8.00	—	—	0.413	—
	9.00	—	—	0.431	—
	9.50	—	—	*	*
	10.00	—	—	—	0.541
$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-glygly-ImH}$ 1 : 1 : 1	10.50	—	—	—	0.572
	11.00	—	—	—	0.593
	11.50	—	—	—	0.628
	4.00	0.052	—	—	—
	5.00	0.061	0.287	—	—
	6.00	0.187	0.325	0.948	—
	7.00	—	—	0.408	—
	8.00	—	—	*	*
	9.00	—	—	*	*
	9.50	—	—	—	0.535
10.00	—	—	—	0.552	
10.50	—	—	—	0.587	
11.00	—	—	—	0.602	
11.50	—	—	—	0.656	

*Waves due to 2 and 3 are absent, but the analysis is prevented due to adsorption peak.

$\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-glygly}$ (1 : 1) are 1, 2 and 2a which are formed with increasing pH in the same order.

Fig. 1. Polarograms for system Cu-glygly (1 : 1).

Fig. 2. Variation in (a) i_d with pH and (b) $E_{1/2}$ with pH for system Cu-glygly (1 : 1).

value with increase in pH, which is indicative of conversion of the species 2 into the species 2a due to deprotonation.

In a recent investigation, Sato *et al.*² carried out pH-metric and epr studies on Cu^{II}-glygly (1 : 1) system. In the interpretation of the data they missed the formation of the species 1. Formation of this species can not be detected from pH-metric studies as there is no release of proton in the process. Our polarographic investigations clearly indicate complex formation at pH 4.0. The $E_{1/2}$ for the system (-0.054 V vs SCE) is at a much higher negative value compared to that of uncomplexed Cu^{II} ion ($E_{1/2} \approx -0.029$ V vs SCE).

Ternary systems Cu^{II}-glygly-ImH: Sato *et al.*² carried out detailed pH-metric and epr studies on the Cu^{II}-glygly-ImH systems and proved the formation of the species 3 and 4.

We have carried out polarographic studies on Cu^{II}-glygly-ImH in the ratios 1 : 1 : 0.5 and 1 : 1 : 1. The polarograms are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. At

pH 4.0, only one wave appears in both the cases. This wave is similar to that observed for Cu^{II}-glygly (1 : 1). This is evidently due to species 1. At pH 5.0, two waves appear corresponding to species 1 and 2. At pH 6.0 there are three waves. Waves due to 2 and 3 are not fully separated. Analysis by log-plot, however, gives two separate straight lines attributable to two species 1 and 2. As pH is raised further the waves due to species 1 and 2 disappear and only the wave due to species 3 remains. Further increase in pH shows appearance of one more wave at more negative potentials but the analysis of the polarogram is prevented due to

Fig. 3. Polarograms for system Cu-glygly-ImH (1 : 1 : 0.5).

Fig. 4. Polarograms for system Cu-glygly-ImH (1 : 1 : 1).

strong adsorption maximum at -0.450 V. As we go further with pH the wave due to species 3 slowly diminishes and only the new wave remains. This wave is evidently due to the species 4.

The systems Cu^{II} -glygly-ImH as 1 : 1 : 0.5 and 1 : 1 : 1 show nearly similar polarographic behaviour except the following two differences. (i) At pH 7.0 the 1 : 1 : 0.5 system shows a composite wave for species 2 and 3 whereas the system 1 : 1 : 1 shows a single well-defined wave for species 3 (Figs. 3 and 4). This observation is in confirmation of the report of Sato *et al.*⁹. These authors in the epr studies

showed the presence of species 2 and 3 for the system 1 : 1 : 0.5 at pH 7.0 and only species 3 for the system 1 : 1 : 1. (ii) The wave for the imidazole bridged species appears at pH 9.50 in the 1 : 1 : 0.5 system and at pH 8.0 in 1 : 1 : 1 system. This observation suggests that the bridged species is formed at lower pH as the imidazole mole ratio is increased.

D.M.E. behaviour of bridged species 4: The reduction wave for species 4 is diffusion-controlled. The wave height is comparable with that of species 2. It indicates, thus, a two-electron reduction per copper atom. The wave is single, well-defined and reversible. Evidently both the copper atoms of the bridged molecules simultaneously accept two electrons each from the electrode and undergo reversible reduction. The reduction of Cu^{II} in imidazole bridged Cu^{II} - Zn^{II} pair in superoxide dismutase has been suggested to proceed via one of the following two mechanisms¹.

Experimental evidences are more in favour of mechanism (i). The imidazole bridged species of the present study is different in so far as the bridged metal ions on both the sides of the bridging imidazole ion are same. The polarographic characteristics clearly indicate a single step reversible reduction. It appears, therefore, that the electron from the d.m.e. is received at the central imidazole ion and is transferred simultaneously to the two Cu^{II} centres causing two-electron reduction at each of these in the following manner,

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References

1. "Metal Ions in Biological Systems", ed. H. SIGEL, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1991, Vol. 18.
2. K. MATSUMOTO, S. OAI, Y. NAKAO, W. MORI and NAKAHARA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 2045.
3. M. SATO, M. IKEDA, M. FUKUDA, T. IDEDA and J. NAKAYA, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, 136, 47.

4. A. P. BRUNETTI, E. J. BURKE, M. C. LIM and G. H. NANCALLAS, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1972, **1**, 153.
5. H. A. SKUNNER and E. W. TIPPING, *Rev. Chim. Minerale*, 1975, **9**, 51.
6. T. P. A. KRUCK and B. SARKAR, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 2889.
7. H. SIGEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, **14**, 1535.
8. A. KANEDA and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1975, **4**, 137.
9. G. BROOKES and L. D. PETTIT, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 2106.
10. A. GERGELY and I. NAGYPAL, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1104.
11. I. NAGYPAL and A. GERGELY, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1977, 1109.